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Influence of Inflation Rate and Exchange Rate on Profitability of Beverage Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

The main objective of this study was to determine the influence of inflation rate and Exchange rate on profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria. In this study, secondary sources of data collection were solely utilized, and an ex-post facto research design was used. Profit after tax (surrogate of profitability) was extracted from the audited financial report of all seven (7) listed beverage companies in Nigeria, while the data for Inflation and interest rates was collected from the National Bureau of Statistics records. Regression analysis was used to analyze the data using statistical techniques. The result of the study shows the coefficients of independent variables and their respective statistically significant values as: inflation rate ($\beta=-1.795$ & $p=0.004$) and exchange rate ($\beta= 1.042$ & $p=0.079$). From the findings of the study, the inflation rate was statistically significant and negatively influenced the profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria. The exchange rate was found to be statistically insignificant on the profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should employ appropriate strategies towards stabilizing the inflation rate, which will improve the profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria. It was also recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should straighten the exchange rate order to avoid frequent fluctuations of the rate of imported raw materials, which the companies are using for their daily operations in Nigeria.

Keywords: Inflation, Exchange Rate, Profitability, Beverage Companies, Nigeria.

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Influence of Inflation Rate and Exchange Rate on Profitability of Beverage Companies in Nigeria**Introduction**

The desire for any developing country like Nigeria is to ensure rapid growth in industries so as to improve the economy of the country. Beverage companies are critical to every economy in the world, and Nigeria in particular, where beverage companies are essential for the Nigerian economy in both financial contributions and employment terms. In fact, the Flanders investment and trade market (2020) reported on the food and beverage industry market overview that food and beverage processing is Nigeria's largest manufacturing industry. The key categories in the Nigerian beverages market are soft drinks, hot drinks, dairy and soy drinks, milk alternatives, alcoholic drinks and water.

Profitability is considered the bedrock of any profit-making industry; it appears to show how well beverage companies generate earnings by using the resources at their disposal. Profitability measures how efficiently beverage companies make use of their assets from their principal or subsequent revenue generation. It is important to recognize that the profitability of Nigerian beverage companies could be influenced by various factors that restrict it from growing faster than average; these factors can be either internal or external to the beverage companies. The internal factors are those that are peculiar to management and thus can be managed effectively to achieve the desired objective of making a profit. The external factors, which are the macroeconomic variables, are those that are beyond the control of the management.

The Nigerian economy has experienced a series of macroeconomic fluctuations, especially in the area of inflation rate. The macro environment in Nigeria remains in a period of significant uncertainty as the

country continue to experience a series of instability and volatility in macroeconomic variables. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2024) current inflation figures release on food inflation in June 2024 is 40.87% which has been a significant concern for beverage companies in Nigeria since inflation makes the cost of production to increase, thereby beverage firms have got no option but either to absorb it or pass it to the consumer by increasing the price of beverages, which may negatively impact the profitability of these companies. Fluctuations in the exchange rate have also affected the import and export of beverage companies, especially of raw materials and finished products imparting further on their profitability. Exchange rate fluctuations can increase the cost of production and lower the revenues of a company using the exchange rate to determine between prices of its products that are exported and those sold domestically. In this regard, the fluctuations may reduce and lower the profitability of any such company.

The researcher observed from the report of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the National Bureau of Statistics that the inflation rate has been fluctuating over the years. In the years 2015, 2016 and 2017, there was an increase that rose sharply to 9.01%, 15.70% and 16.50%. In the years 2018 and 2019, there was a decline from 16.50% to 12.01% and from 12.01% to 11.40%. In the years 2020, 2021 and 2022, there was an increase in inflation rate, which was 13.25%, 16.95% and 18.85%, and it continues to rise in 2023 and 2024, which were 24.52% and 33.18%. The researcher also observed that there has been a currency depreciation between naira and dollar such that the exchange rate rose from ₦159/\$1 in 2013, ₦168/\$1 in 2014, ₦197/\$1

in 2015, ₦305/\$1 in 2016, ₦306/\$1 in 2017, ₦307/\$1 in 2018, ₦307/\$1 in 2019, ₦380/\$1 in 2020, ₦413/\$1 in 2021 and ₦449 in 2022. Furthermore, in 2023 and 2024, the exchange rates were ₦645.92/\$ and ₦1,479.68/\$. Between 2013 to 2024, the naira kept depreciating against the dollar, which is one of the major culprits of inflation and a determinant factor of profitability in beverage companies.

The influence of macroeconomic variables on the profitability of beverage companies has remained unresolved by researchers due to the frequent increase and rise of inflation and exchange rates, especially in developing countries and Nigeria in particular. Consequently, since the Nigerian economy has been characterized with fluctuations in macroeconomic variables, the researcher has decided to scientifically use secondary data to examine the influence of fluctuations in inflation rate and exchange rate during the years of this study and relate it to the changes in profitability of beverage companies in

Nigeria covering the period 2014-2023 so as to ascertain their negative influence or otherwise. It is against this background that this study deems it important to find out the influence of inflation rate and exchange rate on the profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria.

Following the objective of the study, hypotheses were tested as follows:

H₀₁ Inflation rate has no significant influence on profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂ Exchange rate has no significant influence on profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

The study is based on the concept of inflation rate, the concept of exchange rate and the concept of profitability. The conceptual framework is represented in Figure 1, which demonstrates the two independent variables (inflation and exchange rates) and one dependent variable (profitability)

Figure 1: Dependent and Independent Variables

Sources: researchers design, 2024

Concept of Inflation

Inflation is an increase in the price of goods and services over a period of time. An economy is said to be experiencing inflation when the average price of products and services in that economy is climbing at an ever-increasing rate over time (Ali-Momoh & Fajuyagbe, 2022). According to Rogers and Wang (2015), inflation is a rise in the general level of prices of goods and services in an economy over a period of time. According to Romer (2019), it is the gradual or average

increase in the prices of goods and services in a certain economy over time. Kiganda (2014) defines inflation as the general and persistent increase in price level, and has negative impact on the stability of the macroeconomic environment.

Concept of Exchange Rate

Exchange rate is the value of one currency in terms of another currency (Krugman, Obstfeld, & Melitz, 2021). Exchange rate is the price at which a unit of a country's currency is valued for another country's

currency at any point in time. The price at which the Nigerian Naira is valued for United States Dollars, Pounds, and Euros is the exchange rate. Sari, Ayu Nur Indah (2019) explains that the exchange rate can reduce investor confidence level because the foreign currency exchange rate will affect the costs and benefits of "playing" in trading goods, services, and securities. A favourable exchange rate will lower the cost of living, especially for developing countries that rely heavily on imports like Nigeria.

Concept of Profitability

Profitability refers to the extent to which an activity yields financial gain or profit. Warren and Reeve (2016) state that profitability is the ability of a company to generate revenue (profit). A firm's ability is determined by how well and efficiently it operates and the resources they have at its disposal. Profitability is commonly used as an indicator of corporate performance (Kant, 2018). It shows the ability of a company to make a profit on turnover, asset level, and capital stock over a specific period (Odusanya, Yinusa, & Ilo, 2018). Nguyen and Nguyen (2020) defined profitability as one of the critical factors in assessing performance, showing the percentage of profit compared to asset investment, stock, or sales. Companies can increase their profits by effectively protecting themselves from external forces that affect their ability to achieve higher prices or lower costs. Profitability measures efficiency; it is the extent to which a company earns profit. In the determination of whether to invest in a company or not, potential investors evaluate the company's profitability to establish resource utilization and management of its investment Portfolio (Benjamin, Emmanuel, Francis & Ben, 2019). The company must be aware that profitability is the first thing to attract investors (Dao, 2016).

Empirical studies

Ehiedu (2020) researched the influence of macroeconomic factors on financial institutions' return on assets in Nigeria during a ten-year period, from 2009 to 2018. The researcher used exchange rate, interest, and inflation to measure macroeconomic factors, while banks' return on assets was used to assess banks' performance. The data collected were analysed using least squares multiple regression. The research work found that the rate of interest has a beneficial impact on financial institutions' return on assets. Exchange rate and rate of inflation have a negative but minor impact on the return on assets of financial institutions.

Dewi, Soei, and Surjoko (2019) looked at the influence of macroeconomic variables on companies' profitability in Indonesia for the period 1998 to 2016. The study considered the following macroeconomic factors: rate of unemployment, rate of change in currency rate, gross domestic product, and cost of living rate. Return on assets was used to determine a company's profitability. The researchers employed descriptive statistics and a regression model to analyse the data. Results revealed that only the gross domestic product has a substantial impact, whereas inflation, unemployment, and the currency rate have a negligible effect on return on assets.

Adefulu and Adedipe (2018) researched the macroeconomic factors that affect the stock returns of non-financial firms in Nigeria. Specifically, they found that the inflation rate and exchange rate negatively impact stock returns, while the GDP growth rate has a positive effect. Interest rate was found to have an insignificant impact on stock returns. The study examined the relationship between macroeconomic factors and stock returns of non-financial firms in Nigeria. The authors used a sample of 50 non-financial firms listed

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on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) between 2005 and 2015. The independent variables used in the analysis were inflation rate, exchange rate, interest rate, and GDP growth rate.

Yinusa and Ilo (2018) carried out a study on the impact of the Inflation rate and Interest rate on the profitability of 114 non-financial firms measured by Return on Asset from 1998 to 2012. The system GMM employed discovered a significant and negative association between INR and firm profitability. Additionally, IR had negative and significant relations with profitability, contemplating that soaring borrowing costs from financial institutions harmed profitability.

Egbunike and Okerekeoti (2018) investigated macroeconomic factors, firms' characteristics and financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The research study employed a sample of twenty-one consumer products-producing firms that were quoted on the Nigerian stock exchange from 2011 to 2017. The authors measured financial performance using return on assets, whereas macroeconomic aspects were measured using rate of exchange rate, real GDP growth rate, rate of interest and rate of inflation. Firm size and financial leverage were used to assess the companies' qualities. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics and a multiple linear regression. According to the findings of the research work, interest rates and currency rates have no significant impact on asset returns. Return on assets is influenced by the rate of inflation and the rate of growth of the gross domestic product. Also, return on assets is influenced by firm size and financial leverage.

Theoretical framework

The study is based on the uncertainty-bearing theory of profit because it posits that inflation rate and the exchange rate may influence

profitability. The Uncertainty Theory of Profit was proposed by American economist Professor Frank H. Knight in his classic book *Risk, Uncertainty and Profit* (1921). Knight's theory of profit is one of the major theories of profit that starts on the foundation of the risk theory of profit by F. B. Hawley (1893). Knight agrees with Hawley that profit is a reward for risk-taking; that is, how much risk the entrepreneur will bear during the production determines the amount of profit enjoyed by him. But Knight classified risk into insurable (foreseeable) and non-insurable (unforeseeable). According to Knight, insurable risks which are foreseeable and can be measured, their probability of occurrence can be statistically calculated. The risk of fire accident, marine accident, theft, flood, and death by accident is insurable. These risks are borne by the insurance company. The premium paid for their insurance is included in the cost of production. According to Knight, these foreseen risks are not genuine economic risks eligible for any remuneration of profit. Therefore, these insurable risks do not cause uncertainty that might affect the profit of a business firm.

However, some events which cannot be predicted accurately or whose probability of occurrence cannot be easily estimated are known as uninsurable risks, as they cannot be known and foreseen. Knight asserts that entrepreneurs' profits are directly related to uncertainty, which arises from unmeasurable risk such as competitive risk, cyclical risk, technical risk, risk of demand and risk of government intervention (change in government policies and laws especially price control, tax policy, import and export restrictions, changes in exchange rate, interest rate among others) which might reduce the profits of the firms. Therefore, in examining the Influence of inflation rate and exchange rate on beverage companies, the uncertainty bearing theory of profit is sufficient given that

the theory assumes that profit arises because of unforeseeable and non-insurable risks. The uncertainty bearing theory of profit provides ideal theoretical foundations for the study since the study considers some macroeconomic variables that were captured in this theory.

Methodology

This paper employed an ex post facto research design since the data employed were based on past events relating to the inflation rate and exchange rate, and the profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria. The population of the study consists of all seven listed beverage companies in Nigeria on the Nigerian stock exchange as of 31st December 2023. The paper relied solely on secondary data that was collected from documented evidence. The profit after tax was extracted from the audited annual report of accounts of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. On the other hand, data relating to the inflation rate and exchange rate in Nigeria were collected from the website of the National Bureau of Statistics and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) annual statistical Bulletin. The data was collected from 2014 to 2023, giving a total of 70 time series observations.

For the purpose of this study, the multiple regression equation was formulated as follows:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
PAT	70	-329.38	174.36	-12.9137	82.16172
IFR	70	-21.69	47.40	10.9663	20.25627
EXC	70	-15.68	55.60	17.1230	21.50415

Source. SPSS Regression Result, 2024

It can be seen from Table 2 that the mean (average) value of profitability is -12.9137, suggesting a negative value around the centre

$$PAT_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1(IFR)_{it} + \beta_2(EXR)_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where PAT, IFR and EXR are Profit after tax, inflation rate and exchange Rate, respectively. Therefore, the choice of explanatory variables is based on their theoretical relationship with the dependent variable. These variables and their specifications are as follows.

Table 1: Dependent and independent Variables and their proxies

S/No	Variables	Proxy	Variable Specification
1	Profit After Tax	PAT	Dependent
2	Inflation Rate	IFR	Independent
3	Exchange Rate	EXR	Independent

Source: Author’s Compilation (2024)

Results and discussion

Table 2 presented the analysis of the study’s variables in order to fully understand the features, characteristics and behaviour of the data that was analyzed via the use of descriptive statistics to determine the central tendency for the data.

of the profitability, indicating that the beverage companies experienced a loss over the period of investigation. The minimum

average value of profitability was recorded as -329.38, while the maximum average value is 174.36, indicating a relatively wide range for the data series. The wide range between the minimum and maximum values is a pointer towards the relatively high level of variability within the series of the variable. The study established the standard deviation of profitability as 82.16172 suggests a high degree of variation from the mean and that the data are more spread out over a large range of values.

It can also be further seen from Table 2 that the mean (average) value of inflation rate is 10.97, suggesting that positive values around inflation indicate that prices of beverages positively increased during the years investigated. The standard deviation of 20.16172 indicated a high dispersion of the values of the inflation rate series. The minimum and maximum values of inflation range from -21.69 to 47.40. This suggested that the positivity of the increase was relatively double compared to the drop in inflation during the period of investigation.

Table 2 also established that the average (mean) value of exchange rate is 17.12, suggesting a positive value around the centre of exchange rate. This is an indication that Naira has depreciated over the period of investigation. The standard deviation of exchange rate stood at 21.50415. The exchange rate minimum and maximum values for exchange rate are presented as -15.68 to 55.60. The result revealed that the range between the least and highest value of exchange rate is relatively wide, meaning that the percentage increase in the data series almost dominated the percentage decrease in the exchange rate.

Table 3 presents the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test results for all the dependent variables and independent variables,

respectively. The table and its analysis are given below:

Table 3 Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root (ADF) Test for Stationarity of Variables

Variable	ADF Statistic	Stationarity	Order of Integration
Profit After Tax (PAT)	-7.99***	Yes	I(0)
Inflation rate (IFR)	-10.62***	Yes	I(0)
Exchange rate (EXC)	-6.93***	Yes	I(0)

Source: EViews12 stationarity test, 2024

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels respectively

It can be seen from Table 3 above that the results of Augmented Dickey-Fuller for profit after tax, inflation rate, and exchange rate present test statistics of -7.99, -10.62 and -6.93, respectively, with the p-value of 0.000 for all the variables. The critical values of this test at different significance levels of 1% and 10% are -3.472813 and -2.576739. By comparing the test statistics and the critical values of this test, it is clearly revealed that the test statistics are more negative than the critical values at all levels. Thus, the result concluded that the time series data is stationary for all the variables as the ADF test statistics have more negative values than the critical values at a significance level of 1%, and integrated of the order I(0). Therefore, the result rejected all the null hypotheses and accepted that certain attributes of the data do not change over time. Meaning that the data series for all the variables does not have a unit root, thus, they are stationary in nature.

In this study correlation matrix was used as a statistical technique to evaluate the

relationship between the variables (dependent and independent) under study. The matrix is a table in which every cell contains a correlation coefficient.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

	PAT	IFR	EXR
PAT	1		
IFR	-0.254	1	
EXR	-0.028	0.641	1

Source. SPSS Correlation Matrix Output, 2024

Table 4 clearly revealed the positive and negative correlations between the variables in the Sharpe ratio model. The table indicated a weak relationship between profitability and the two other independent variables, as the results produced -0.254 and -0.028, respectively. In terms of magnitude, the lowest negative correlation is -0.028, which is between PAT and EXR, and the highest positive is 0.641, which belongs to IFR and EXR, meaning that there is a strong relationship between the two independent variables.

Collinearity Diagnostics

The possibility of collinearity between the independent variables was investigated using the variance inflation factors. The results are presented in Table 4.10

Table 5: Collinearity Test Results for Sharpe Ratio

	Centered VIF
Inflation rate	1.86
Exchange Rate	1.29
Mean VIF	1.86

Source: Collinearity Test Results, 2023

Table 5 shows that the highest VIF values for inflation rate and exchange rate are 1.86 and

1.29, respectively. The table also shows that the mean or average VIF for all the variables is 1.86. This shows that the VIF values are by far below the threshold values of five set by this study. Thus, the VIF values for the model did not exhibit any significant evidence of collinearity among the independent variables.

In this study, regression analysis was conducted, and the results were produced in Table 6 for easy analysis and interpretation.

Table 6: Regression Model Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Sig
IFR	-1.795	0.604	0.004
EXC	1.042	0.570	0.072
R			0.721
R-Squared			0.518
Adjusted R-Squared			0.504
Durbin-Watson Statistics			1.684
F-statistics			3.960
p-value			0.012

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

Therefore, the regression equation for this study is thus;

$$\text{Predicted profitability} = -16.411 - 1.795(\text{IFR}) + 1.042(\text{EXC})$$

Table 6 reveals that inflation rate has negative significant influence on profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. The magnitude of the negative effect of inflation rate was recorded at -1.795, and was found to be significant at 5% level. This suggests that a

1% increase in inflation rate leads to a proportionate decrease of -1.79% on profitability. It is also obvious from the table that the standard error of estimating the coefficient of inflation rate is 0.604, which cannot be considered as why when compared to the value of the coefficient itself. In addition, Table 5 reveals that exchange rate has a positive impact of approximately 1.042, but the positivity is statistically insignificant on profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. This means that a unit of 1% increase in exchange rate will lead to an increase of 1.04% in profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. The table reveals further that the coefficient of inflation rate was estimated subject to an insignificant standard error of approximately 0.57.

Table 6 shows the coefficient of R-value as 0.721, which can be considered good and is taken for further analysis. R-Square, which is the coefficient of determination of independent was indicated as 51.8% of the variance in profitability. It is required to have a difference between R-square and Adjusted R-square minimum. In this case, the value is 0.504, which is not far off from 0.518, so it is good. The Durbin-Watson is used to detect the presence of autocorrelation in the residuals (prediction errors) from regression analysis. The test statistic values between the ranges of 1.5 to 2.5 are considered normal. In this study, the value of 1.684 falls within this range; the study would not consider autocorrelation to be a problem in this regression model. The regression model predicts the variables significantly fit well since the P-value (0.012) is less than 0.05, meaning that, overall, the regression model is statistically significant, so we can conclude that the independent variables reliably predict the dependent variable.

Discussion of Findings

This paper examined the influence of inflation rate and exchange rate on beverage companies in Nigeria. The study established a negative influence of inflation rate on the profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. The magnitude of the negativity of the influence of inflation rate was recorded at -1.795, and it was found to be significant at 5% significance level. Therefore, the study accepted the idea that inflation rate has a statistically significant influence on profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria during the period of investigation. Thus, the study rejected the null hypothesis (H_{01}) of this study since the significance value was recorded as 0.004, which is less than the p-value of 0.05. The result agreed with the findings of Adefulu and Adedipe (2018), Yinusa and Ilo (2018) and Egbunike and Okerekeoti (2018), who established a significant but yet adverse contribution of inflation.

The study established that exchange rate is statistically insignificant, but it still recorded a positive contribution on profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. Therefore, the study disagrees with the assumption that exchange rates have a statistically significant influence on the profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria during the period under study. Thus, the study accepted the null hypothesis (H_{02}) of this study since the significance value of 0.072 is greater than the p-value 0.05. The result of this study confirms the findings of Ehiedu (2020), Dewi, Soei, and Surjoko (2019), and Egbunike and Okerekeoti (2018), who established an insignificant and positive contribution of the exchange rate.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the influence of inflation rate and exchange rate on beverage companies in Nigeria over a period of 10 years, spanning 2014-2023. Therefore, based

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on the findings, it is concluded that inflation rate has a significant negative influence on the profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. The study also concludes that exchange rate is statistically insignificant, though it recorded a positive influence on profitability of listed beverage companies in Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the Federal Government of Nigeria should apply more strategies towards controlling inflation to a single digit so as to improve the profitability of beverage companies in Nigeria. Finally, the study recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should stabilise the exchange rate in order to avoid frequent fluctuations in the rate of imported raw materials that the companies are using for their daily operations in Nigeria.

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